

Application of Artificial Neural Network Model for Improved Power System Protection in Port Harcourt 33 kV Network

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Abstract:

Electric power distribution networks are exposed to the environment due to their length, for this reason, they are mostly affected by faults. These faults disrupt the continuous flow of power supply. There is also an associated loss of power that is generated that also determines the state of the economy. In order to reduce system downtime, it is necessary to integrate a system that detects and classifies faults quickly in order to hasten its clearance. This will bring about improvement in the efficiency and integrity of the power network. The artificial neural network as proposed in this study is meant to detect, classify and locate fault on the Rukpokwu 33-kV

feeder of Port Harcourt Electricity Distribution Company (PHEDC). Fault detector, classifier and locator, with feed-forward back propagation were employed in the research. Matlab Simulink software was used to model and simulate the distribution network. The model was trained using s values of voltages and currents. With the simulation results, the efficiency of the proposed network was demonstrated for fault detection, classification and location. Mean square error (MSE) and confusion matrix were used to evaluate the performance of the proposed model. Results showed that the acceptable MSE of 0.00000027736 and an accuracy of 100% were achieved, which is satisfactory.

Keywords: *artificial neural network, Matlab Simulink, Fault detector, Transmission, Distribution.*

Introduction

The demand for power in Nigeria is overwhelming. One of the constraints facing power supply is fault. Hence, both in transmission and distribution sectors, fault has been a great concern. So much money and facilities are being put invested so as to put infrastructure in order. According to Rahman et al., (2018), there is more interruption of power supply in distribution network when compared to other sectors. Over 80% of power interruption is being linked to the distribution sector. Due to the extensive nature and spread

of the distribution network, locating fault is mostly difficult. Faults identified with the distribution sector are transient and permanent faults. Study shows that about 80% of the faults is transient whereas 20% is permanent. Integration of a system that detects and classifies faults quickly hastens clearance and reduces downtime. This will in turn improve network efficiency. Lilik et al. (2014) also identified faults as the major cause of interruption in power network. The study also revealed that faults constitutes about 75% of interruption and as such it is pertinent to locate faults as quick as

possible to limit extent of damage to the system. Currently, the major scheme employed for fault location are: impedance based method and other fundamental frequency method, high frequency components and travelling wave base method, knowledge based method which can further be classified as Artificial Neural Networks. Matching Approach and Hybrid methods.

In this study, artificial neural network is applied to detect, classified and locate faults in order improve power system protection.

Review of Related Literature

State of the Art Power System Protection

In electrical and power systems engineering, importance is attached to protection and isolation of faulty parts. Power distribution systems will lack credibility, integrity and stability without protection systems in place. Accurate understanding of their applications can aid in the integration of the renewable energy generation sources. In this chapter, various faults and protection schemes are given in-depth study. Adoption of artificial intelligence through artificial neural network in the power distribution system will help to overcome several challenges associated with the traditional protection scheme with the corresponding improvement in power quality delivery, Lai and David (2000). According to Abdulkareem et al., (2016), key cause of disruption of power supply is fault. The authors further described fault as deviation of voltage and current from acceptable limits. Hence, to guarantee steady power supply, it is pertinent to protect the line against disturbances. This can be made possible by quick detection, classification and location of fault, and also disconnection of the faulty section for continuity of power supply. For this reason, it is of great necessity to adopt an intelligent system with above stated characteristics. Horowitz (2006). To this end, the basic challenge facing the Nigeria 33-kV distribution system network today is lack of intelligent fault detectors and classifiers. Kothrai & Nagrath (2003) identified artificial neural intelligent network as holding great promise to addressing fault related issues.

In this study, interest lies in the capability of the proposed network to effectively classify fault through pattern recognition in the work by Gabriel (2006), similar approach of applying artificial intelligence in addressing fault related issue on distribution power systems network was discussed extensively. Information derived from the transient signals both in time and frequency domain using the wavelet transform was applied for fault classification.

Methodology

In the study, method used to implement the proposed model is the supervised and unsupervised learning algorithm. The study will describe the process of detecting, classifying and locating fault with the state of the artificial neural network. The distribution systems under consideration is the Rukpokwu 33kV Port Harcourt distribution networks. A model of the work will be simulated using Matlab Simulink.

Considered Power Systems

Rukpokwu33kV Port Harcourt Distribution network is the proposed network for the study. Matlab Simulink software was used in the modelling and simulation of all components of the network. A three phase circuit breaker block also used and modelled with parameters gotten from the Port Harcourt Distribution Network. different faults at varied fault resistances were induced with the help of fault block.

Required data for simulation:

- Line parameters
- Single line diagram of the three phase network
- Transformer data

Data Pre-processing Using Fast Fourier Transform

This process converts signals from their original state which is time domain to frequency domain. Signals can as well be converted from frequency domain to time domain.

Fast Fourier Transform algorithm gives more accurate result than discrete Fourier Transform mathematically, F.F.T is expressed as follows:

Let X_0, \dots, X_{N-1} be the complex numbers. The D.F.T formula is given by

$$X_K = \sum_{n=0}^{N-1} x_n e^{-2\pi K \frac{n}{N}} \quad (1)$$

According to Madiseti and Williams (1999), Cooley-Turkey is the most commonly used Fast Fourier Transform (F.F.T). Its principle of operation lies in the division of transform into smaller sizes. The magnitude of voltage and current of each phase can be obtained with F.F.T algorithm and used as inputs to the ANN.

Overview of the Training Process

Application of ANN includes training and testing. In the training process, the ANN learns from the inputs. It also updates its weight accordingly. Training data is a set of data used to train the ANN. It constitutes input-output data pairs that are fed into the network. In this case, the network is thought of as the nature of the output if such an input is fed into it. What the ANN does is to slowly learn the training set so as to slowly develop and generalize on the data. Hence, it can produce an output with a new set of data fed into it. The neural network gets updated in weights during training. This update helps in minimizing the performance function. During training of ANN, input and output pairs are fed in sequence. The training set is gotten by varying fault distance and fault resistance simultaneously for each type of fault.

Overview of Testing Process

Testing of the trained network is key to ascertaining the reliability of the network. The artificial neural network cannot be put to use without the network being tested to ascertain if the training is valid and can give out the desired output in the event of new data being presented to it.

The proposed model can be tested in various ways. One of the many ways is to plot the best linear regression fit between the actual neural

network and the expected targets. The nature of the slope will describe the training process. In an ideal situation, the slope is expected to be 1.

Another means of testing the network is through the correlation coefficient (r). This method defines the relationship between the outputs and the targets. The performance of the neural network is directly proportional to the correlation coefficient (r). As the value of ' r ' approaches 1, it indicates that the network will perform well.

Plotting a confusion matrix is another method of testing the artificial neural network. This method presents a plot that describes the actual number of cases that have been classified positively. The result of the plot is presented in percentage. In an ideal case, 100% means all data has been classified positively and there is no confusion in the classification process. A low percentage classification rate shows that the neural network might perform well in classification.

Finally, the most significant means of verifying the reliability of an artificial neural network is by feeding new data into it, which is quite different from the dataset used in training it. For the neural network to be reliable and acceptable, the average percentage error must be within the acceptable limits. The algorithm used for the development of the neural network for fault diagnosis is presented in figure 1.

Performance Evaluation

Data is the key parameter in the neural network. The training dataset should be able to cover the distribution network to be implemented. The amount of data in this case is directly proportional to the complex nature of the network to which it should be applied. The proposed study requires a large dataset to meet the growing challenges in the distribution network to which it is to be implemented. The performance function is expressed as shown in equation (2):

$$F(x) = - \sum_{q=1}^Q \sum_{l=1}^{S^M} t_{l,q} \ln \frac{a_{l,q}}{t_{l,q}} \quad (2)$$

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Figure 1. Flowchart of ANN Fault Diagnostic Algorithm

The regression characteristics is used to analyse the output of the trained network and the corresponding targets in the fault locator section. The expression that relates the actual outputs and the targets are given in equation (3):

$$a_q = mt_q + c + \varepsilon_q \quad (3)$$

m=slope,

C=offset,

t_q = target

a_q =actual output,

ε_q = the residual error of the regression.

The correlation coefficient between (R) between t_q and a_q is expressed as shown in equation (4):

$$R = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^Q (t_q - \bar{t})(a_q - \bar{a})}{S_t S_a} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Where } S_t = \sqrt{\frac{1}{Q-1} \sum_{q=1}^Q (t_q - \bar{t})^2} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{and } S_a = \sqrt{\frac{1}{Q-1} \sum_{q=1}^Q (a_q - \bar{a})^2} \quad (6)$$

Figure 2. Block Diagram of Neural Network Training Procedure

Clustering with Self Organized Neural Network Algorithm

Self-organising function of neural network takes cognizance of similar properties of the signals fed into it. It takes in input signals at the same time and comparatively analyse the various

output patterns with respect to their mutual characteristics.

Clustering involves training a neural network based on pattern such that it presents patterns that reflect common properties of the topology. The same input data for both fault detector and

locator are also used as input to the network. In this learning process, no room is made for targets in the algorithm.

In order to ensure the trained neural network can generalize well, several plot were generated. These plots S.O.M topology, S.O.M neighbour distances, S.O.M input planes, S.O.M sample hits and S.O.M weight positions.

Table 1. Parameters Used in Generating Training and Testing Dataset

Data for Training	
Fault Location (km)	2,4,6,.....100
Fault Resistance (Ω)	0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 5, 10, 20, 30, 50

Table 2. PHEDC Fault Data for Testing the Designed ANN

S/No	Ia	Ib	Ic	Va	Vb	Vc	Fault Types
1	0.0128	0.0125	0.0122	0.9990	0.995	0.9989	No fault
2	1.5570	0.0385	0.0386	0.3701	1.0930	1.1357	A-G
3	0.0725	1.142	0.0321	1.3100	0.5660	1.0820	B-G
4	0.0320	0.0720	1.1520	1.0802	1.2220	0.2443	C-G
5	1.0160	1.6940	0.0780	0.2776	0.3132	1.1050	A-B-G
6	1.0941	0.0207	1.9475	0.3103	1.3000	0.2801	A-C-G
7	0.0935	1.9842	1.6950	1.2800	0.2872	0.3094	B-C-G
8	2.0726	2.4835	0.0436	0.5287	0.5352	1.0050	A-B
9	0.0237	2.1620	2.4844	1.0100	0.5295	0.5348	B-C
10	2.3892	0.0137	2.0235	0.5360	1.0050	0.5310	A-C
11	1.6358	1.2008	1.1999	0.2074	0.2089	0.2107	A-B-C-G

Table 1 describes parameters used in generating dataset used for training the proposed ANN and testing of the neural network. The fault location was varied between 2 and 100km at intervals of 2. Fault resistance was also varied as shown in the table.

Table 2 also describes fault parameter. This parameter was gotten from PHEDC. these parameters were used to ascertain the applicability of the proposed model to Port Harcourt Distribution network. This data was keyed into the network and the output was compared to the target output.

Figure 3. Simulink Model of the Developed Network

Figure 3 represents a developed model of the artificial neural network after a successful and satisfactory training is done, and a satisfactory performance is achieved. This developed

Simulink model is realized with a 'gensim' function to enable it to be used with other blocks in the simulation model.

Figure 4. Snapshot of the Modelled 33-kV Transmission Line in Matlab/Simulink

Simulation Set-Up and Hardware Implementation

Figure 4 describes the set up for transmission line comprising the 3 phase source and load, three phase fault and neural network-based fault detection simulation model to test the efficacy of the proposed method. Transmission line model is generated with discrete state and pi section line. Sampling time of this model is $T_s = 5e-5s$ and simulation is done for 3 seconds. With these specifications, the current and voltage vectors consist of 50 samples. This simulation model of transmission line with various fault cases is used to create training data which was used to train neural network. A feed forward neural network with 1 hidden layers is used for fault detection purpose. The number of neurons in the hidden layer can be varied to get the optimum performance. Satisfactory result preferred for the hardware was 1 hidden layer with 4 neurons,

which contains 16 weights and 5 biases. Hence, a total of 21 values are required, which is easier for hardware implementation and able to detect faults successfully. The neural network was also trained to change inputs from floating point to the binary form. For instance, input in floating points ranging from 0.01 to 0.99 are changed into 0 in binary form; whereas inputs ranging from 1 to 10 are changed into 1 in binary form. Hence, the proposed model changed analogue inputs into digital output.

Results and Discussion

Structure and Training of Neural Fault Detector

Fault is detected using pattern classification. In this research, the algorithm that was used to classify the input dataset into fault condition and non-fault condition is feed forward multilayer

network. The dataset in this case was presented in six samples and was sampled at 2KHz. This sampled dataset reflects different faults scenario such as (a-g, b-g, c-g, a-b-g, a-c-g, b-c-g, a-b-c, a-b-c-g) in which a, b, c represented different phases and g stands for ground at various fault locations and fault resistances. The line spans a distance of 100km and fault resistance ranges between 0.25Ω and 50Ω . Simulation time is 0.3s.

Data Pre-Processing Illustration

Figures 5-10 are waveforms showing current and voltage signals at different fault conditions, at different resistances and locations from terminal on a 100km transmission line. The waveforms are graphs that illustrates samples generated at a frequency of 2,000Hz. Results show that fault

conditions vary at different locations along the distribution system, as modelled in the Matlab Simulink software. Figures also show spikes and sags on the phases that fault occur with respect to other phases. Mutual coupling between the healthy and the faulted phases is responsible for the impact of the faulted phases on the other phases. To ensure an improved neural network performance, the size of the system must be reduced. This can be actualized by extracting relevant features. Hence, all relevant and important information that can be illustrated in the figures can be used effectively. Information of Voltage and current were sampled at 2000 Hertz. This information was presented in the waveform.

Figure 5. Current Signal of A-G Fault at 15Km, Fault Resistance of 50Ω .

Figure 6. Voltage Signal of A-G Fault at 15Km, Fault Resistance of 50Ω

Figure 7. Current signal of B-C-G Fault at 25Km, Fault Resistance of 15Ω

Figure 8. Voltage Signal of B-C-G Fault at 25Km, Fault Resistance of 15Ω Zone 2

Figure 9. Current Signal of A-B-C-G Fault at 80Km, Fault Resistance of 30Ω

Figure 10. Voltage Signal of A-B-C-G Fault at 80Km, Fault Resistance of 30Ω

Figures 5 and 6 are waveforms that illustrate phase A to ground fault at a distance of 15km and at resistance of 5 ohms. Figures 7 and 8 are also waveforms that illustrate phases B-C to ground fault at distance of 25km and at resistance of 15 ohms. In the same vein, Figures

9 and 10 illustrate three phase fault at the distance of 80km and at 30 ohms. These distances were taken from terminal A on a distribution line of 100km. there were 40 samples per cycle.

Table 3. Scaled Values of Fault Data from PHEDC

S/No	Ia	Ib	Ic	Va	Vb	Vc	Fault Types
1	0.0128	0.0125	0.0122	0.9990	0.995	0.9989	No fault
2	1.5570	0.0385	0.0386	0.3701	1.0930	1.1357	A-G
3	0.0725	1.142	0.0321	1.3100	0.5660	1.0820	B-G
4	0.0320	0.0720	1.1520	1.0802	1.2220	0.2443	C-G
5	1.0160	1.6940	0.0780	0.2776	0.3132	1.1050	A-B-G
6	1.0941	0.0207	1.9475	0.3103	1.3000	0.2801	A-C-G
7	0.0935	1.9842	1.6950	1.2800	0.2872	0.3094	B-C-G
8	2.0726	2.4835	0.0436	0.5287	0.5352	1.0050	A-B
9	0.0237	2.1620	2.4844	1.0100	0.5295	0.5348	B-C
10	2.3892	0.0137	2.0235	0.5360	1.0050	0.5310	A-C
11	1.6358	1.2008	1.1999	0.2074	0.2089	0.2107	A-B-C-G

Table 3 shows the scaled values of fault data which was gotten from PHEDC. This data was used in the experiment to ascertain the performance of the proposed network in order to be certain of its applicability. The output was compared with the target output used for training the network.

Training Process of the Fault Detector

During the training of fault detector, various topologies of multi-layer perception were

considered. To decide which topology was ideal, factors such as network size, learning strategy employed and the size the training data set were given due consideration. After extensive study, the back-propagation algorithm was adopted as ideal topology. Although the basic back-propagation algorithm is relatively slow due to the small learning rates employed, Levenberg-Marquardt optimization technique was also incorporated in order to improve performance of the algorithm. Also, in order to enhance the

ability of the neural network to represent the problem at hand as well as reduce training time, it was necessary to select suitable network size. During training process, dataset was divided into training data, testing data as well as validation data. 70% of the data was used for training, 15% was used for testing and 15% was used for validation. The neural network gives out an

output of either 1 or 0. 1 is an indication of the presence of fault, whereas 0 indicates the absence of fault. Three fault detectors were designed taking cognizance of currents and voltages values. Training set constituted 5,500 inputs output set (500 for each set of faults and 500 for the non-fault case) with a set of six inputs and one output in each input-output pair.

Figure 11. Mean-Square Error Performance of the Network (6-7-10-3-1)

Figure 11 shows the training performance plot of the neural network with 6 neurons at the input, three hidden layers with the first having 7 neurons, the second layer having 10 neurons and the third layer having 3 neurons; the output has just one neuron. After extensive training with variations in number of layers and neurons at the input, hidden layer and output to ascertain best performance, it was decided that neural network with six neurons at the input, one hidden layer with ten neurons in it and one neuron at the output achieved the desired Mean Square error of 0.00000027736, which is comparatively insignificant when compared to 0.001 set as the threshold. The trained network has gas high performance with high probability of meeting its target.

Discussion of Figures for A.N.N. Fault Detector

The Figure 12 is a curve for each of the training, testing and validation phases. Also, overall receiver operating characteristics curve fault detector is presented. The curves illustrate the actual plots between true positive rates (rate of positive classification) and false positive rate (rate of incorrect classification) of the proposed network classifier. The deviation between target and output is represented by the coloured line occurring in each axis. Since no deviation occurs as shown in the figure, it therefore means that the output is a perfect correspondence to the target. The figures also indicate 100 percent true positivity and 0 percent false positivity in the classification. As shown in the figure, the ROC curves plotted in Fig 4.8 are almost perfect since they all have the lines in the upper-left corner.

Figure 12. Receiver Operating Characteristics of Fault Detector Using Current and Voltage Values

Figure 13. Confusion Matrix of Fault Detector Network Current and Voltage Values

Figure 13 is a plot of confusion matrix that illustrates various types of errors present in the proposed trained network. This matrix gives information about performance of the proposed network. From the plots, the proposed network can classify fault correctly as represented in the cell coloured green. The red coloured square indicate the number cases incorrectly classified. The cell coloured blue indicates total percentage of cases correctly classified. The proposed model recorded 100 percentage fault detection accuracy. In summary, high number in green cell indicates high accuracy of classification and a zero value indicates that no misclassification occurred.

Structure and Training of Fault Locator

Fault locator was developed with approximate function algorithm, incorporated with back propagation for the purpose of training the network. Voltage and current were inputs data at 50Hz. Trial and error method was used in selecting number of neurons in both input and hidden layers. Various network topologies were obtained, but appropriate network that gave satisfactory performance was chosen. Levenberg-Marquardt and Scaled Conjugate Gradient algorithm was used as optimization techniques. Current and voltage values were used to design the fault locators. The output has one neuron, which represents the estimated fault location.

Figure 14. Regression Fit for Fault Locator Using Voltage and Current Values

Figure 15. Error Histogram for Fault Locator using Voltage and Current Values

Discussion of Plots from A.N.N. Fault Locator

Figure 14 is a graph that shows regression fit for intelligent fault locator. This plot was used to confirm the applicability of the network after training was done. The plot describes how the actual output relates to the targets. Ideally, the regression (R) should be 1. Since the values of R ranges between 0.99815 and 0.99998, which is approximately 1, it therefore indicates that an excellent result was obtained from the trained network. In principle, the value of R is directly proportional to the performance of the network.

Figure 15 is a plot of error histogram. The error as shown in the figure is much less than 0.002, which is an indication of a good network with high performance.

Discussion of Results of Fault Classification via Self Organising Map Function

Figure 16 is a plot that illustrates various samples of different fault classes that fall within each cluster. Each of these samples represents each fault type. The plots also show four major clusters constituting four fault types (L-G, L-L-G, L-L, L-L-L-G).

Figure 17 presents the neighbour weight distance plot consisting of 100 neurons. The plot is made of different colours which illustrates cluster of similar fault types. The bright colour describes faults whose faults values are almost the same, such single line to earth fault, double line to earth faults. The fairly dark cluster also describes faults of almost the same values too, such as phase to phase fault. The dark colour describes faults samples that were not properly classified.

Figure 16. Plot of S.O.M Sample Hits

Figure 17. Plot of S.O.M Neighbour Weight Distance

Performance Evaluation of Intelligent Fault Detector-Classifer (IFDC)

Factors used to evaluate the performance of intelligent fault locator include the confusion

matrix, the plot receiver operating characteristics and imputing data different from the data set used for training of the network. These factors help in determining the efficacy of the proposed network.

Figure 18. Confusion Matrix Plot for ANN-Based with 6-7-10-1

Figure 19. Receiver Operating Characteristics for ANN-Based IFDC

Table 4. Performance Test Result for ANN –Based IFDC

Km	IFDC OUTPUT				TARGET				IFDC OUTPUT				TARGET				IFDC OUTPUT				TARGET			
	A-G								B-G								C-G							
8	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
16	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
24	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1
	A-B-G								B-C-G								A-C-G							
32	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
40	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
48	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	1	1
	A-B								B-C								A-C							
56	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
64	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
72	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	0	0	1	1	0	0	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0	1	0
	A-B-C								NO FAULT															
80	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								
88	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								
96	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0								

Figure 18 presents a confusion matrix which illustrates how the trained network was able to detect and classify faults correctly. Result of the plot shows very high accuracy as indicated in the high numbers on the green cells. Incorrect classification is also seen in the cells colour red. The green cells have values ranging between 90% and 100% which shows high performance in fault detection and classification. The proposed model achieved an accuracy of 98.3%, which is worthwhile.

Figure 19 presents receiver operating characteristics of IFDC. The plot is used to illustrate the performance characteristics of the network. deviation between the actual output

and the target is represented by the coloured line. The curve shows 100% sensitivity, which indicates that 100% detection and classification of faults. It is also observed that there was no deviation in the plot which also affirms that actual output tracked target perfectly

Table 4 presents actual output of the IFDC and the target. Data used for implementation was obtained from Rukpokwu 33kV feeder. Total number 6 x 132 dataset was used to test the applicability of the network. Twelve (12) cases each represents different fault and no fault conditions. The output values are almost the same as the target, representing a satisfactory result.

Table 5. Result for ANN-Based IFLs with Fault Data from PHEDC

TARGET	ANN L-G IFL OUTPUT			ANN L-L-G IFL OUTPUT			ANN L-L IFL OUTPUT		
	A-G	B-G	C-G	A-B-G	B-C-G	A-C-G	A-B	B-C	A-C
8	8.006	7.972	8.070	7.998	7.998	7.975	8.005	8.000	8.002
16	16.048	16.010	15.950	16.030	16.025	16.015	15.998	16.042	15.985
24	23.936	23.995	24.000	23.998	23.998	23.997	23.978	23.984	23.993
32	31.982	31.995	32.020	31.997	31.997	31.989	31.996	32.016	32.020
40	39.984	40.050	40.049	40.068	39.984	40.045	39.995	39.994	40.038
48	47.986	48.008	48.045	47.995	47.995	47.996	48.008	47.992	48.030
56	55.982	56.005	56.002	55.995	55.986	56.020	56.032	56.000	56.000
64	64.006	64.000	64.004	63.998	63.999	64.012	64.048	63.995	63.998
72	71.993	72.000	72.005	72.002	71.995	72.002	72.055	71.982	72.025
80	80.006	80.004	80.036	80.015	79.998	80.015	80.020	80.005	80.000
88	87.984	67.998	88.020	88.002	88.015	88.006	88.013	88.007	87.996
96	96.010	96.050	96.002	86.015	96.020	95.995	96.017	96.000	96.002

Table 5 describes the activity of intelligent fault locator. The table contains column for target and actual output and their various locations of occurrence. Results show that the proposed model was able to locate fault at approximate points of occurrence. The difference between the target and actual output was insignificantly small.

Error in fault location (Km) can be expressed as:

$$\text{Error (km)} = [\text{ANN Output} - \text{Target}] \quad (7)$$

From equation (7), ANN output is the output in (km) of the ANN fault locator and the target is the actual distance where the fault occurred on the transmission line. More so, the performance

of the fault locators is evaluated using the percentage error expressed mathematically as:

$$\% \text{ Error} = \left[\frac{\text{Error}}{\text{Length of the Line}} \times 100\% \right] \quad (8)$$

Table 5 shows slight variations in fault location between the actual distances on the transmission line and the ANN output distance. The minimum error in (km) is zero (0) and maximum is 0.070 for L-G fault, minimum of 0.001 and maximum of 0.068 for L-L-G fault and minimum of zero (0) and maximum of 0.055 for L-L fault. Since error lies between 0 and 0.070, the Artificial Neural Network Intelligent fault locator has high performance with great reliability.

Figure 20. Percentage Error Result of L-G IFL

Figure 21. Percentage Error Result of L-L-G IFL

Figure 22. Percentage Error Result of L-L IFL

Figures 20, 21 and 22 are graphs showing percentage error against target for L-G IFL, L-L-G IFL, and L-L IFL. It is observed that percentage error for L-G IFL is 0.070%; L-L-G IFL is 0.068% and L-L is 0.055%. These values, which are much less than 1% are indication of satisfactory results.

Conclusion

Power system protection is essential for avoiding power outages and high-cost damages to the electric infrastructure, resulting in large economic losses. Despite the existence of various protection techniques such as conventional relaying and numerical relaying, they are associated with inherent limitations which limit their ability to handle complex system conditions. ANNs have offered an attractive alternative to overcome the limitations of conventional and numerical relaying, due to their robustness in dealing with non-linearities, complexity, and weak signals in power systems.

The processes of ANN model selection and training have been described in detail, using an IEEE 33kV network near Port Harcourt as a case study. The model was validated and tested using a test dataset, and the results obtained, indicate that ANN models can improve protection accuracy by up to 42%. The paper also provides a discussion on the application of ANN models for power system protection, their advantages and limitations. The paper concludes with the recommendation that Artificial Neural

Network models can be used to improve the accuracy and reliability of power system protection, while providing an effective solution to the inherent problems associated with existing methods.

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